

ANNEXE. Organizational competencies for BIM adoption

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Annexe 1 - Description of variables

Code	Description
M01_01	<i>Understand the business benefits of using BIM tools and workflows</i>
M01_02	<i>Identify the business risks from using BIM tools and workflows</i>
M01_03	<i>Define the role senior management plays in promoting BIM Implementation within an organization</i>
M02_01	<i>Identify the availability of clear BIM Implementation leadership within an organization</i>
M02_02	<i>Adoption of a common BIM Implementation vision has been adopted by senior leaders/managers</i>
M03_01	<i>Formulate a BIM Implementation Strategy for an organization</i>
M03_02	<i>Identify overall BIM Goals for an organization</i>
M04_01	<i>Identify the changes to organizational processes necessary to benefit from BIM Software Tools and Model-based Workflows</i>
M04_02	<i>Define a hierarchy of responsibilities needed to improve Internal BIM Workflows</i>
M04_03	<i>Establish competent BIM-enabled teams to participate in tenders or BIM-projects as required by Client or General Contractor</i>
M05_01	<i>Advise clients on the competitive advantages of using BIM Models on projects</i>
M06_01	<i>Identify all issues related to Intellectual Property (IP) and ownership of BIM Models or Model Components</i>
A01_01	<i>Generate the processes and templates necessary to facilitate BIM Implementation within an organization</i>
A01_02	<i>Apply metrics to monitor the progress (or lack of progress) of BIM Implementation within an organization</i>
A01_03	<i>Organize initiatives to encourage staff to adopt BIM tools and workflows within an organization</i>
A02_01	<i>Apply standardized metrics to measure the financial performance of BIM Projects</i>
A02_02	<i>Establish project costs based on BIM Deliverables rather than on the number of 2D Drawings required</i>
A03_01	<i>Develop dedicated policies to motivate staff to adopt new technologies and processes</i>
A03_03	<i>Conduct software-specific Skill Assessments</i>
A04_01	<i>Define organization-specific BIM Roles</i>
A05_01	<i>Develop a BIM Capability Statement</i>
A06_01	<i>Procure BIM Models, Model Components or related consultancy services from specialized BIM Service Providers</i>
A06_02	<i>Assess the BIM Capability of Project Partners, Project Participants, or BIM Service Providers</i>
A07_03	<i>Develop BIM-specific Contractual Clauses that clarify who owns the model/s or its components</i>
A08_01	<i>Identify and evaluating the risks associated with Collaborative BIM Projects</i>
A09_01	<i>Develop a Quality Management System which assesses & monitors the quality of BIM Models, Model Components and other Deliverables</i>
A09_02	<i>Assess the quality of documentation against established national or international standards</i>
F01_01	<i>Develop a software use policy that differentiates between proprietary and non-proprietary file formats</i>
F02_01	<i>Develop a documented procedures to deal with information flows during Collaborative BIM Projects</i>
F03_01	<i>Act as a BIM Facilitator during the delivery of Collaborative BIM Projects</i>
F04_01	<i>Deliver a project according to Employer's Information Requirements</i>
F04_04	<i>Organize models, documents, project information, cost information and specifications according to standardized Classification Systems</i>
F05_01	<i>Develop a list of activities and tasks necessary to initiate, conduct and review BIM Projects</i>
F05_02	<i>Use Content Management Systems or Document Management Systems to manage information storage and sharing</i>
I01_01	<i>Develop a BIM Implementation Strategy to guide an organization's BIM adoption efforts</i>
I02_02	<i>Define a process to check the quality of Model Components against established Modelling Standards</i>
I03_02	<i>Use specialized tools to organize and manage Model Components</i>

I04_01	<i>Document the repetitive activities and tasks required to initiate, conduct and review BIM Projects</i>				
I04_02	<i>Develop BIM Software Tool templates for use on different types of BIM Projects</i>				
I05_01	<i>Develop a detailed BIM Training Plan</i>				
I05_03	<i>Develop a BIM Training Programme</i>				
I05_04	<i>Develop a Skill Register, a Training Log or like track existing and newly acquired staff skills within an organization</i>				
I05_05	<i>Act as a dedicated in-house BIM Trainer</i>				
I06_02	<i>Investigate the suitability of Internal BIM Workflows after a BIM Project has been delivered or completed</i>				
I06_03	<i>Use checklists to conduct procedural audits on Internal BIM Workflows</i>				
I07_01	<i>Developed a BIM Guide or BIM Manual for use by an organization</i>				
I07_04	<i>Document lessons learned, recommendations or best practices from completed BIM Projects</i>				
I07_03	<i>Generate BIM Management Plans for an organization</i>				
T02_01	<i>Use BIM Software Tools on active projects</i>				
T02_02	<i>Use Graphical Algorithm Editors like Dynamo or Grasshopper</i>				
T02_06	<i>Use Software Extensions that further extend the functionalities of BIM Software Tools</i>				
T02_08	<i>Use Model Servers or BIM SaaS solutions</i>				
T04_01	<i>Use BIM Software Tools to generate accurate Error-Free Models</i>				
T05_01	<i>Generate 3D construction details from BIM Models</i>				
T07_01	<i>Develop checklists, task lists or flow charts to guide Technical Staff in how to generate or check BIM Models</i>				
T07_02	<i>Generate high-quality IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) model files from proprietary BIM Software Tools</i>				
T07_04	<i>Use Model Progression Specifications or a similar system to manage the Level of Development within BIM Models</i>				
T07_05	<i>Establish a set of Naming Protocols covering models, components, parameters, details, etc.</i>				
T07_06	<i>Work in a Common Data Environments</i>				
T08_01	<i>Use a Content Management System or a Document Management Systems to manage information storage and sharing</i>				
S01_01	<i>Develop procedures to manage which software version to use and when to deploy it</i>				
S02_01	<i>Identify data types which can be exchanged (or should not be exchanged) with Project Partners</i>				
S02_02	<i>Develop software, hardware and network deployment and upgrade procedures</i>				
S03_01	<i>Develop procedures to deploy, replace or upgrade hardware</i>				
S04_01	<i>Establish the needed number of software licences to enable all trained users to operate at the same time</i>				
S04_02	<i>Assist in troubleshooting software issues related to BIM Software Tools</i>				
S05_01	<i>Develop software tools/extensions to improve the Project Deliverables of off-the-shelf software tools</i>				
R01_01	<i>Monitor the technological developments which may affect the competitive position or deliverables of an organization</i>				
R02_01	<i>Identify an organization's BIM Goals and BIM Objectives</i>				
R03_01	<i>Develop non-technical Training Material to assist staff in understanding the business and process requirements of BIM</i>				
R03_02	<i>Share BIM Knowledge with others through a newsletter, blog or similar</i>				
R04_01	<i>Develop a Knowledge Management Strategy</i>				
R04_02	<i>Conduct surveys to understand the BIM experiences of staff</i>				
R05_01	<i>Align Human Resource policies with BIM Implementation processes</i>				
R06_01	<i>Conduct focus groups or workshops to harvest the BIM experience of staff within an organization</i>				
R06_02	<i>Participate in academic research focusing on BIM adoption, innovation, or education</i>				
R06_03	<i>Publish white papers, reports or similar that encourage industry to adopt BIM Workflows and processes</i>				
R07_01	<i>Develop strategies to encourage industry-wide BIM adoption and innovation</i>				
ISO_3.8.2	<i>Have tools & processes in place to maintain Asset Information Models so that they continually meet organizational objectives</i>				
ISO_2.1.2	<i>Define project information requirements</i>				
ISO_2.1.3	<i>Define project information delivery milestones</i>				
ISO_2.3.5	<i>Produce mobilization plans for production teams</i>				
ISO_2.6.3	<i>Verify project information models in accordance with information production methods and procedures</i>				
ISO_2.2.2	<i>Have the tools and processes in place to make reference information and shared resources available during Projects</i>				
ISO_3.1.10	<i>Link different enterprise systems to improve access to organizational, project and asset information</i>				
ISO_2.4.1	<i>Verify the completeness of designation documents for the main designed part</i>				
ISO_2.1.1	<i>Identify BIM resources and requirements for a BIM project</i>				
O03_02	<i>Generate the majority of 2D Drawings needed on a project out of 3D BIM Models</i>				
O06_01	<i>Generate COBie specifications using applicable tools and templates</i>				
O01_01.X	<i>Model Uses - Capture and represent</i>				
O01_01.1	<i>Surveying</i>	O01_01.2	<i>As-built representation</i>	O01_01.3	<i>Visual communication</i>
O01_01.4	<i>Generative design</i>	O01_01.5	<i>3D detailing</i>	O01_01.6	<i>2D documentation</i>
O01_01.7	<i>Laser scanning</i>	O01_01.8	<i>Photogrammetry</i>	O01_01.9	<i>Record keeping</i>
O02_01.X	<i>Model Uses - Planning and Design</i>				
O02_01.1	<i>Lean process analysis</i>	O02_01.2	<i>Value analysis</i>	O02_01.3	<i>Conceptualization</i>

002_01.4	<i>Concept development</i>	002_01.5	<i>Disaster planning</i>	002_01.6	<i>Construction planning</i>
002_01.7	<i>Demolition planning</i>	002_01.8	<i>Erection planning</i>	002_01.9	<i>Operation planning</i>
002_01.10	<i>Urban planning</i>	002_01.11	<i>Space programming</i>	002_01.12	<i>Specification and selection</i>
003_01.X	<i>Model Uses - Simulation and Quantification</i>				
003_01.1	<i>Accessibility analysis</i>	003_01.2	<i>Acoustic analysis</i>	003_01.3	<i>Constructability analysis</i>
003_01.4	<i>Energy Consumption analysis</i>	003_01.5	<i>Lighting analysis</i>	003_01.6	<i>Finite element analysis</i>
	<i>Environmental impact</i>				
003_01.7	<i>analysis</i>	003_01.8	<i>Visitor flow analysis</i>	003_01.9	<i>Construction operation analysis</i>
003_01.10	<i>Reflectivity analysis</i>	003_01.11	<i>Risk analysis</i>	003_01.12	<i>Security analysis</i>
003_01.13	<i>Site analysis</i>	003_01.14	<i>Spatial analysis</i>	003_01.15	<i>Structural analysis</i>
003_01.16	<i>Sunlight analysis</i>	003_01.17	<i>Safety analysis</i>	003_01.18	<i>Thermal analysis</i>
003_01.19	<i>Code control and validation</i>	003_01.20	<i>Clash detection</i>	003_01.21	<i>Cost estimation</i>
003_01.22	<i>Wind study</i>	003_01.23	<i>Life cycle assessment</i>	003_01.24	<i>Quantity takeoff</i>
	<i>Fire and smoke</i>				
003_01.25	<i>simulation</i>	003_01.26	<i>Augmented reality simulation</i>	003_01.27	<i>Virtual reality simulation</i>